
INTERNET MEDIA IS A BOON - CONDITIONS APPLIED

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Abstract

The present scenario of the society shows that internet media has become a part and parcel of our daily life. People cannot imagine their routine without accessing internet. It has washed out the geographical boundaries are almost. The major negative side of using internet as social mass media is that it's a virtual world and whatever information found on internet are readily accepted without any kind of verification. Keeping safety measures while using internet is always advisable. As two sides of a coin internet media has its advantages and disadvantages. It is at the users' end how they utilize it. A framework proposed involving three aspects in order to aware people and develop a positive use of internet. It is suggestive that not only proper use but restricted use of internet is also to be emphasized on. It can be proven as a best resource of knowledge and skills at the same time can be a worst destroyer of time, money and energy. It depends on the utilization of the internet and completely in the hands of internet users to make it bane or boon.

Introduction

Perhaps no one was aware about potential of internet when it was created and gradually entered in our lives. But in present time it has become a part and parcel of our daily life. People cannot imagine their routine without accessing internet. Social media system has brought people so close that political and geographical boundaries are almost deteriorated. The concept of netizenship is evolved which may overtake the concept of citizenship. It has become communication gateway and helps to strengthen relationships. In information society, bonds grow stronger. We are connected with the people we do not know or places we did not visit in our whole life through whatsapp face book, twitter, instagram etc.

The biggest and serious loophole of using internet as social mass media is that it's a virtual world and whatever information found on internet are readily accepted. Cross verification of the information is almost zero. So, fake information and news goes viral within no time through social media. Sometimes it creates an illusionary perception that we are closer to each other as it may be only virtually and not physically or emotionally. Posting likes and wishes to people have become so mechanical. The influence of mass media has an impact on many aspects of the human life like social relations, studies, marketing, entertainment, time management and many more.

Advantages

- It educates people providing ample of information regarding various areas such as social, health, environment, entertainment, different countries, geographical, whole world and what not.

- It removes a barrier of distance. It makes us update with latest news and happenings around the world.
- No need to wait for opportunity and to search platform to bring out hidden talents. Talented people are appreciated and they can earn name as well as fame in their field of choice. People upload videos showing their talents of cooking, mimicry, comedy, acting, dancing and singing etc. And they may become viral all over the world.
- People get the latest news in a very short time. People get news daily through the media and this keeps them updated with current affairs.
- Best platform for advertisement and promotional events of various products.
- Internet Media leads to exposure of different cultures. It showcases different cultural practices.
- Children's knowledge increases. Children can learn as per their need, time and places from various educational apps, quiz programs, animal programs, other informative programs and so on.

Disadvantages

- One cannot control the way of approaching Internet as a media. It sometimes contains the adult content which should be restricted for children. Limiting children's access to such content can be difficult.
- People spend rather waste too much time on the internet. Sometimes people unknowingly become addicted to the internet and they forget their family, relatives and friends. They do not bother about their neighbors.
- Internet as a form of media is an open stage for fraud and hacking.
- Access use of mobile, computer causes health problems. It may cause weak eyesight, back pain, hearing defects, obesity etc.
- Sometimes it is misused to harass, to abuse, to black mail, for cyber crimes and to misguide people. It's very easy for one to create an anonymous account. And such accounts can be used to for malicious purpose such as spreading rumors.
- Social media is addictive like alcohol or cigarettes. It has addictive qualities which people cannot keep them away from it.
- Spending more time on social networking sites may cause adverse effect on mood, poor mental health, anxiety and sometimes depression.

Safety Measures

- Avoid posting personal information online. Do not open your personal details and photos for people online to misuse them. Even professional and confidential details should also be protected from online sharing. We must utilize privacy setting while sharing posts online. Both web browsers and mobile operating systems have privacy settings available to protect your data. Social websites like Facebook also have privacy-enhancing settings available.
- Be alert to practice safe browsing. Avoid exploring dangerous content because lurid are used by cybercriminals as bait. Just one careless click can expose personal details or infect your device with malware. Don't give a chance to hackers by exploring dubious content. Make sure your

device is secure with internet browsing safety, secure Wi-Fi network and virtual private network which enable us to have a secure connection between our device and Internet. Update antivirus program regularly. Though internet security software cannot protect against every threat, but it can remove most of the malware.

- Be careful while you download and don't download suspicious apps or come from a site you don't trust. Make passwords as strong as it becomes difficult to demystify for cybercriminals. Password should be unique and complex. One can take help of password manager software so that you don't forget them. Minimum 15 characters long, mix letters, captions, numbers and special characters.

Proposed Framework

A triangle framework is proposed to channelize proper utilization of internet. The mentioned framework has three major aspects in form of suggestions keeping internet utilization in a wise manner.

(A Triangle Framework)

Rules and regulations:

It is at the end of government and policy makers to form strict rules and regulations in order to control malpractices on internet media as well as continuous check on the observance of those rules must be systematized. To stop adverse affects of internet media- fake news, antisocial or antinational actions on internet media must be punishable with immediate effect. Misinformation warfare spread in a fraction of moment that is dangerous than conventional warfare. Internet media has the potential to create a slow-paced disaster. Strict actions must be taken against cyber crimes. People should be well aware about rules and legal actions for malpractices online media.

Education:

Education is the powerful medium to spread awareness regarding safe utilization of internet. Education system must include how to do sensible use of internet media and how one can utilize this facility safely, meaningfully without being harmful to his self, society, nation and the world. Education

is a platform where children can be enriched with ethics and values. Thorough inculcation of core elements and values amongst children can bite their conscious during misuse of internet media. Content related to proper utilization of internet should be included in the curriculum and syllabus at school and higher education level. Schools should arrange co-curricular activities in order to educate students for safe surfing on internet. Schooling and higher education are the right time to make students aware about malpractices on internet media and to make them courageous enough to raise their voice against abuses or culprits.

Internet can be a most effective medium for self learning. Infact many educational programs, software and educational apps are available for teachers, students, and other stake holders. It provides effective teaching and learning aids to gain knowledge and skills. Teacher plays a vital role to make their students understand about usefulness of internet media in academics. So that students utilize it genuinely instead of exploring malware.

Society:

On the top we find parents and family when we talk about involvement of society in promoting wise use of internet media. All the family members must spend time with each other instead of getting themselves engaged in virtual world of social media. Parents must make their children aware and alert related danger sides of internet media. Parents, relatives should keep watch to their younger ones in order to save them from unhealthy posts on social media. Usually parents are role models for their children and so they should set an example not to spend too long on mobiles. Sometimes parents need to understand first about misuses of internet. People in society should arrange activities in order to promote safe surfing on internet.

Thus as mentioned in the proposed framework enough work out at these three aspect can definitely aware people and develop a positive use of internet. It is suggestive that not only proper use but restricted use of internet is also to be emphasized on.

Conclusion

A coordinated regulation and wise use of internet are necessary to make it of good use. Internet has potential to strengthen and also to weaken relationships. It can bring unknown people closer and apart close people. It can save the time, can waste time as well as kill the time. It may enhance studies and also disturb it. It can create as well can destroy. The proposed framework emphasize on three aspects to channelize genuine use of internet. All those three aspects can spread awareness about pros and cons of internet usage. It depends on the utilization of the internet and completely in the hands of internet users to make it bane or boon.

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